

CoPc 2D and 1D Arrangement on a Ferromagnetic Surface

Emilia Annese,^{*,†,‡} Carlos E. ViolBarbosa,[‡] Giorgio Rossi,^{¶,‡} and Jun Fujii[‡]

[†]*Department of Physics, Università degli Studi Modena e Reggio Emilia, via Campi 213/A,
I-41100 Modena, Italy*

[‡]*TASC Laboratory, IOM-CNR, SS 14, km 163.5, I-34149 Trieste, Italy*

[¶]*Dipartimento di Fisica, Università degli studi di Milano, Via Celoria 16, 20133 Milano,
Italy*

E-mail: emiliaannese@gmail.com

Phone: +39 (0)40 3758409

Abstract

We studied the adsorption of CoPc in two-dimensional (2D) arrangement on Fe films grown on Cu surfaces and in monodimensional (1D) arrangement on iron nanowires by scanning tunnelling microscopy and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). We observed the molecular electronic states at the interface concomitant with Co(Pc) magnetic moment coupling with the substrate magnetization.

CoPc 2D arrangement turns into 1D by using a facet surface as a template. CoPc molecules on iron nanowires are weakly interacting with the substrate manifesting a substantial $3d_z$ spectral feature in XAS spectrum. Both CoPc 2D and 1D arrangements can open up new interesting scenarios to tune the magnetic properties of hybrid interfaces involving metallorganic molecules.

Introduction

Precisely controlled fabrication of low-dimensional molecular structures with tailored spin properties is at the heart of recent researches. Self-assembly of organic molecules and/or atoms carrying specific spin information on well-defined template surfaces is one viable approach. Representative examples of the attempts in this direction include the growth and manipulation of two (2D) and one (1D) dimensional organic molecule self-organized network with characteristic spin alignment. For instance, the specific magnetic anisotropy of 2D supramolecular network of organic molecules on Cu(100) surface has been tailored by oxygen addition.¹ The magnetic moment of paramagnetic iron-porphyrine 2D films are stabilized and controlled by their adsorption on ferromagnetic (FM) surface.² More recently, highly ordered Co-phthalocyanine (CoPc) chains formed on a stepped metallic surface present electrons propagating along the step arrays establishing a precursor phase toward realization of one dimensional (1D) charge/spin transport.³

We report on the arrangement, the electronic and the magnetic properties of CoPc molecules in contact with iron film grown on low index Cu planes and iron nanostructures grown on vicinal Cu surface. CoPc is a quasiplanar heterocyclic macrocycle molecule with high conjugation. The Co atom placed in the center of the macrocycle has an electronic configuration and magnetic moment that depends on the ligand field and can be modified when in contact with metallic substrates.⁴⁻⁶ Fe thin film grown on Cu is a prototype of magnetic system for studying molecule adsorption. Fe films grown on Cu(111) are bcc and ferromagnetic at room temperature in-plane easy magnetization axis for films thickness above 5 monolayer (ML).⁷ When grown on Cu(100) surface, Fe films assume a pseudomorphic fcc-structure for thickness below 8-10 ML (depending on the growth conditions).⁸ This structure exhibits ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic coupling between the monoatomic layers.⁹ For this study, we grew a 20 ML Fe film on Cu(111) and 5ML Fe film on Cu(100). We have already reported in Ref.⁴ that the Co(Pc) magnetic moment aligns parallel to the in-plane magnetization of the substrate. Here, we show that the magnetic coupling of CoPc to the iron substrate force

out-of-plane orientation when Fe film magnetization is out-of-plane (5ML Fe on Cu(100)). The configuration of CoPc is determined by the interaction between the Co central atom and neighbouring iron of the substrate, independent of the Fe structure (fcc or bcc). We observe that the interaction between the molecule N atoms and the substrate is different for the Fe 5ML and Fe 20 ML, as a consequence of the differences in the atomic coordination on these Fe surfaces. The coupling between CoPc and iron film is substantially limited to the first contact layer of molecules, i.e. those that undergo a limited hybridization with the substrate that drives their electronic and magnetic configuration. The density of electron states in the proximity of Fermi edge (E_F) dominated by iron extended and surface states. Photoelectron spectroscopy shows nevertheless a broad peak at ~ 0.6 eV of binding energy that is related to the molecular state and the symmetry character of additional CoPc state at 2.3 eV. We also analyse the case of CoPc 1S structures that can be adsorbed on iron nanowires obtained by growing on a selectively oxidized Cu vicinal surface.

Experimental

Samples preparation and characterization were performed at the APE beamline of IOM-CNR at the Elettra Synchrotron Radiation Facility (Trieste, Italy).¹⁰ Cu(111), Cu(100) and Cu(332) substrates were prepared in UHV by several cycles of Ar⁺ ion sputtering and annealing. Iron is deposited on the Cu substrates by an electron beam evaporation source in a base pressure of 10^{-8} Pa at room temperature (RT). The quality of as grown Fe surface was probed by low energy electron diffraction (LEED), X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS) and X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD). LEED patterns were observed with a primary e-beam of 124 eV for both Cu(111) and Fe films. The Fe 20 ML-thick films were post-growth annealed at 370 K for 20 minutes. In Figure 1 (a)- (b) we report the diagram of pseudomorphically iron fcc and bcc that highlights the different iron-iron distance and neighbourhood in the two films. The Cu(332) surface is vicinal to Cu(111), with a

nominal miscut of 10° . Oxygen dosing induces on Cu(332) a striped pattern composed of alternating oxidized Cu(110) facets and atomic clean Cu(111) terraces of tunable width.^{11–13} Iron nanowires were grown by depositing Fe 0.3 ML that self assembles on the oxidized strips of the Cu(332) surface reproducing a pattern with an average periodicity of 4nm.¹² Hereafter we refer this system as Fe-O-Cu surface. CoPc was subsequently deposited on Fe films and Fe-O-Cu surfaces at RT by molecular beam effusion from a resistively heated quartz crucible. All thicknesses were calibrated by a quartz micro-balance. A mask was used during the deposition of the CoPc to expose only half of the sample to the molecular beam resulting in two distinct sample regions. Linearly polarized radiation from the APPLE-II type undulator with electric field (\mathbf{E}) oriented in or perpendicular (p , s polarization) to the storage ring plane was used for both angle resolved photoemission(ARPES) and X-ray absorption spectroscopy(XAS) measurements. A SES2002 electron energy analyzer was used for ARPES measurements. XAS and XMCD spectra were acquired by collecting the total electron yield with an electrometer in the experimental geometry illustrated in Figure 1(1) and (2)-(3), respectively. The energy resolution was 150 meV. An in-situ electromagnet could apply a pulsed magnetic field up to ± 0.1 T along one direction in the sample surface plane (Figure 1 (2))or (with a second electromagnet) along the sample normal (Figure 1 (3)) XMCD was measured on samples in remanent magnetization by reversing the photon helicity. A careful removal of background of the XAS spectra in the Co L-edge region was obtained by subtracting from the CoPc XAS spectra the one measured on the bare substrate.⁴ Here, we present the XMCD signal normalized by the L_3 XAS intensity that allows to evaluate the magnetic signal per unit atom. Scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) images were acquired in-situ with an atomic resolution apparatus, operating at RT. STM images are recorded in constant current mode and processed using the WsXM software.¹⁴ The sample bias voltage is referred with respect to tip. The schematics of CoPc molecule is reported in the last panel of Figure 1.

Figure 1: Upper panels: pseudomorphically Fe fcc(a) and Fe bcc (b) structures. Experimental geometry of XAS(1) and of XMCD measurements in-(2) and out-of-plane(3). Schematic representation of the Co-Phthalocyanine.

Results and discussion

Morphology of CoPc on ultrathin Fe films

Figure 2 (upper panels) displays the morphology of Fe films on Cu surfaces vs thickness. Figure 2 (a) shows the STM image of the Fe 20-ML-thick film grown on Cu(111). The film presents three-dimensional Fe clusters with an average lateral dimension of $16 \times 20 \text{ nm}^2$ uniformly distributed on the Cu surface. The LEED pattern of the film (inset of 2.a) exhibits the Cu(111) diffraction pattern with various satellites spots. Those are interpreted as bcc Fe(110) domains with different in plane orientation with respect to the Cu(111) surface.^{15,16} Figure 2 b shows STM image of the Fe 5-ML-thick film grown on Cu(100). The image indicates an epitaxial growth of the first layers, whereas the outmost Fe layers form monoatomic oblong islands with lateral dimensions ranging from $6 \times 7 \text{ nm}^2$ to $24 \times 29 \text{ nm}^2$, and a height of 0.2 nm. The Figure 2 (bottom panels) shows the CoPc adsorption on Fe films. CoPc molecules are identified by the four-lobed pattern related to the charge in the four aromatic rings of the Pc structure and central Co atoms. The molecules appear to

Figure 2: STM images of (a) 20ML Fe film grown on Cu(111) and (b) 5ML Fe film grown on Cu(100) before the CoPc deposition. (c) 1ML CoPc deposition on the Fe 20ML-thick film. (d) 0.1ML CoPc deposition on the Fe 5ML-thick film. Bias and tunneling current of the images: (a) $V_b = 0.8$ V, $I = 0.6$ nA; (b) $V_b = 0.8$ V, $I = 0.342$ nA; (c) $V_b = 1$ V, $I = 0.322$ nA; (d) $V_b = 0.169$ V, $I = 0.5$ nA. Inset presents LEED pattern of (a) Fe films. (e)-(f) topographic images of CoPc obtained as enlargements of the images (c) and (d)

lie flat on the Fe surface. Figure 2 (c) shows the STM image of 1ML CoPc film deposited on the Fe 20-ML-thick film. The molecules organize in two local lattices: rectangular with lattice parameters $1.6 \times 1.6 \text{ nm}^2$ and hexagonal lattice with a molecule-molecule distance of $\sim 1.53 \text{ nm}$.⁴ Figure 2 (d) displays the STM image of 0.1ML CoPc film deposited on the Fe 5-ML-thick film. We observed the presence of isolated CoPc molecules with no preferential orientation. Besides the molecules there are some additional spots in the image which we ascribe either to impurities or molecular fragment. Figure 2 (f) displays an isolated CoPc molecules on Fe 5-ML-thick film, where we can observe a distinct brighter spot centred inside the CoPc. This central spot is ascribed to the d_{z^2} or dxz , dyz orbitals of the Co atoms.

Unoccupied electron states of CoPc on ultrathin Fe films

N K-edge and Co L-edge XAS spectra allow us to address the electronic configuration of CoPc in contact with iron film of different structures. Figure 3 (a) shows the N K-edge spectra of 1 ML CoPc on two iron substrates and a 6ML CoPc reference sample. The data were acquired with p polarized light at incidence angle of $\theta = 0^\circ$ (open symbol) and 60° (filled symbol). The spectrum of 6ML CoPc is the closest approximation to that of the free molecule, due to the weak interactions among molecules and negligible contribution from the buried interfaces: it is used as a reference to recognize the typical features of two chemically distinct N sites: aza-bridge (N_1) and isoindole (N_2). In the dipole approximation, the electron is excited from the initial nitrogen $1s$ state into the final (unoccupied) states: π^* and σ^* whose orbitals point respectively out of the molecular plane and in plane. The 6ML CoPc XAS spectra exhibit a weak angular dependence, indicating a combination of molecular orientations.⁴ By contrast, the $1s - \pi^*$ transitions is strongly suppressed for $\theta = 0^\circ$ (i.e. \mathbf{E} field lying in the molecular plane) in the CoPc(1ML)/Fe samples, implying that N atoms lay in a plane parallel to the substrate for very thin CoPc film and in agreement with the STM results. The residual intensity at about 396.8 eV for $\theta = 0^\circ$ may originate from a rehybridization of the LUMO states localized on some N atoms as already mentioned in previous works.^{17,18} Both CoPc

Figure 3: N K (a) and Co L_3 (b) XAS spectra of CoPc films vs substrates: Fe 20ML and Fe5ML and the reference spectra of CoPc 6ML on Fe 20ML. Measurements are performed at p -polarized light and at $\theta=0, 60^\circ$ ($\theta=45^\circ$) at N K (Co L_3) edge.

1ML films on Fe 20 and 5 ML show broad $1s - \pi^*$ spectral features. The N state with respect to the free-molecule like spectrum is attributed to a direct bonding between the N atoms and the iron film.^{4,5,19} The energy position of N $1s - \pi^*$ transitions varies for each Fe films. In particular CoPc(1ML)/Fe(5ML) exhibits similar intensities for N1 and N2 components, whereas for the CoPc(1ML)/Fe(20ML) and CoPc reference, N1 peak is more intense than N2. The different Fe coordination in the two ultrathin films can be reflected in the different N XAS line shapes. Figures 3(b) displays Co L_3 XAS spectra at $\theta = 45^\circ$ and p -polarization for CoPc 1ML adsorbed on iron films (5ML and 20ML), and 6ML CoPc. The Co $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectra probe the unoccupied s and d states of the molecule as projected to the Co site. The Co atom configuration in CoPc is divalent ($3d^7$) in the ligand field of D_{4h} symmetry; the splitting of the Co $3d$ band is observed as distinct features in the spectrum of 6ML CoPc.⁴ Co XAS spectra for CoPc 1ML adsorbed on Fe 20 ML (Fe 5ML) show similar broadened peak at 774.6 eV of width of 2.2 (1.8) eV, with vanishing feature at 776 eV and reduced one at 772.5 eV. Overall the Co L-edge lineshape is less sensitive to the substrate than the N K edge spectrum: this indicates that the atomic structure of Fe surface affects more strongly

the nitrogen hybridization than Co-Fe bonding suggesting on-top direct interaction of Co and Fe as a driving mechanism for the CoPc on iron surfaces.

Figure 4: STM images of CoPc 1ML (a) and 1.5ML (b) deposited on Fe 20 ML film. (a) $V_b = 1\text{ V}$; $I = 0.322\text{ nA}$; (b) $V_b = 1\text{ V}$; $I = 0.1\text{ nA}$. (c)-(d) N 1s and Co 2p XAS spectra of CoPc 1 and 1.5 ML on Fe 20ML measured at $\theta = 45$ and 30° respectively.

We explored the changes in the molecular arrangement as a function of CoPc thickness for iron-20ML-thick film (Figure. 4 (a)-(b)). STM images of CoPc 1 ML (a) and 1.5 ML (b) on iron-20ML-thick (two different samples) show that the local ordered displacement of CoPc is not anymore observed in the layer above the first one. Figure 4 (c)-(d) compares the XAS spectra of 1ML and 1.5 ML CoPc film on Fe 20ML and the change in N K and Co L₃ XAS the line shape vs CoPc film thickness: the broad features of N K XAS spectrum of CoPc 1 ML are replaced by the two sharp features relative to N1 and N2 sites similarly to 6ML CoPc spectrum; the featureless Co L₃ XAS spectrum of CoPc 1ML leaves the place to a

structured line shape with a peak at 772.5 eV. The behavior evidences that the coupling with substrate is limited to the first "contact" layer of CoPc.

ARPES of CoPc deposited on ultrathin Fe films

The iron density of the states dominates the electronic structure at the interface in the Fermi level region, nevertheless it is affected by the interaction with the molecular overlayer and this is reflected in the ferromagnetism of the interface and the renormalization of the interacting molecular state. We performed ARPES and STM measurements on pristine Fe 20ML film and CoPc(1.5ML)/Fe20ML (STM image, Figure 4 (b)). Photoemission spectra were recorded

Figure 5: ARPES measurements on Fe20ML and CoPc(1.5ML)/Fe20ML. The photoemission spectra measured at 25.5 eV p -polarization at normal emission (a) and at 59 eV p and s polarization at 34 ° off normal emission(along $[\bar{1}10]$ direction of Cu(111))(b). In panel (a) photoemission spectra of CoPc(1ML)/Cu(111) is reported as a reference for the molecular state energy position.

at 25.5 eV (p -polarization) and 59 eV (s - and p - polarization). p (s) polarized photons excite initial state of Fe (CoPc) state of specific symmetry following the selection rule: $A \cdot p$ is even (odd) and only the initial states of even (odd) reflection symmetry contribute to the emission. At the bottom of Figure5(a) the CoPc(1ML)/Cu(111) spectrum is displayed to highlight the density of states features related to interface molecular states. Their observation in photoemission spectra of the valence bands on Fe surface is made difficult by the large cross

section of iron 3d states. The spectra measured at 25.5 eV on Fe 20 ML film (Figure 5(a)) present features at 0.25 and 0.75 eV binding energy (BE). These peaks have been ascribed to surface resonances,¹⁶ and are therefore sensitive to the adsorption of the molecules. The adsorption of CoPc suppresses the peak at 0.25 eV, but the feature around 0.75 eV becomes more intense and broad. This indicates a spectral contribution from the CoPc in this binding energy range. The photoemission spectra were measured with photon energy of 59 eV at 34 ° off normal emission on Fe 20ML and CoPc(1.5ML)/Fe 20ML to be more sensitive to CoPc than Fe film . On bare Fe 20ML we observed a linear dichroism near E_F and no dichroism at 2.3 eV (Figure 5(b)). Upon CoPc deposition the linear dichroism near E_F is suppressed, whereas dichroism appears around 2.3 eV . The latter feature can be related to a contribution of Fe bulk and Co dxy-like or σ states. Overall the Fe DOS is reduced at the CoPc/Fe interface and molecular-induced interface states appear at 0.6 eV (evident in the spectra measured with 25.5 eV) and at 2.3 eV with Co dxy-like or σ symmetry (evident in the polarization dependent spectra measured with 59 eV)

Magnetic properties of CoPc deposited on ultrathin Fe films

By aligning magnetization and photon helicity in XMCD, we verified that the 20 ML-thick Fe film grown on Cu(111) exhibits in-plane easy magnetic axis and the 5ML-thick Fe film grown on Cu(100) exhibits out-of-plane easy magnetization axis. Figure 6(a) shows the XMCD measured for 5MLFe/Cu(100) at 80 K and 20MLFe/Cu(111) at RT. The XMCD were acquired in remanent magnetization, after saturation by an applied H field pulse, upon inversion of the light helicity. Both curves were normalized by the L3 peak intensity of the average line. The Fe $L_{2,3}$ magnetic dichroism is stronger for the 20MLFe/Cu(111). The smaller dichroism of the 5MLFe/Cu(100) is explained by the presence of the antiferromagnetic coupling in internal layers,[?] while the top two layers are ferromagnetic-coupled and make the main contribution to the XMCD signal.[?] The XAS at Co L-edge (Figure 6(b)), measured in the same conditions as the Fe films, indicates that the magnetization of the

Figure 6: (a) Fe L_{2,3} XMCD spectra measured for Fe 20ML(circle), and 5ML (filled-square) films. (b) Co L₃ XAS spectra relative to the parallel I^p (black) and antiparallel I^m (red) orientations of magnetization and light polarization for CoPc(1ML)/Fe 20ML (top panel) and CoPc(1ML)/Fe 5ML(middle panel) respectively. Co L₃ asymmetry $(I^p - I^m)/(I^p + I^m)$, are displayed in the bottom part of the panel (b). Fe (Co) XMCD spectra for sample Fe 20ML were performed in experimental geometry (2), whereas for XMCD Fe(Co) for Fe 5ML in geometry (3) of Figure 1.

CoPc aligns with the magnetization of the Fe film. The bottom panel of Figure 6(b) shows the Co XMCD spectra normalized by the Co L₃ intensity in order to have the magnetic dichroism per unit atom. We have already reported in a previous work⁴ that Co XMCD exhibits the same sign of Fe XMCD for CoPc(1ML)/Fe(20ML) interface at RT. Here, we show that CoPc(1ML)/Fe5ML interface also displays Co XMCD aligned with the underneath out-of-plane magnetized Fe film. The small L₂ XMCD peaks are weak due to the extremely small amount of Co atom present in 1ML of CoPc. However the L₃ XMCD peaks show very similar intensities, in spite of the average magnetization of the supporting 20ML Fe film be at least 4 times larger than the 5ML Fe film. This suggests that the ferromagnetic coupling between molecule and film is dominated by the electronic interaction between Co and the first Fe layer, rather than be ascribed to a magneto-dipole interaction between the film magnetization and Co atoms.

1D CoPc deposited on ultrathin iron nanowires

Iron nanowires were grown onto an optimally oxidized Cu(332) surface displaying alternate parallel stripes of atomic clean Cu(111) and oxidized Cu(110) facets. Iron atoms adsorb on the oxidized facets as a consequence of higher chemical affinity with these stripes than with pure copper terraces.¹² The position of iron atom on Cu(110) facets are highlighted in Figure 7. CoPc deposited on top of Fe 0.3 ML on oxidized Cu(332) adopts different organization depending on the film thickness: it preferentially aligns on the (011) facets Fe-O-Cu in 1D order for 0.5 Å (8 (a)-(c)) or on both (011) and (111) facets for CoPc 1 Å thick film (8(b)-(d)). Iron nanowire along the (011) facet cannot be distinguished anymore in the STM image after molecule deposition, since CoPc adsorbs preferentially along the same stripes and therefore on top of the iron nanostructure. The presence of Fe on the sample along the step is further confirmed by the measurement of Fe L-edge XAS on the CoPc/Fe-O-Cu interface(Figure 9 (a)). By increasing CoPc content the molecules, after saturation of the (011) facet, but start to coalesce and occupy also the (111) terraces. A close-up view

Figure 7: (a) 3D rendering of STM images of Fe 0.5 ML on oxidized Cu(332): $V_b = -0.6$ V, $I = 0.25$ nA.

Figure 8: 2D STM images on CoPc 0.5 (a) and 1\AA (b) on iron nanowire on oxidized Cu(332) surface and its 3D rendering (c) and (d). (a) $V_b = -1.3\text{ V}$, $I = 0.1\text{ nA}$; (b) $V_b = -1.5\text{ V}$, $I = 0.44\text{ nA}$. The insets reproduce 3D rendering of CoPc in (out) (001) facet of Fe-O-Cu system.

of the STM image in the inset of Figure 8 revealed that molecules adsorbed on both facets and terraces show sub-molecular contrast with bright circular spot (Co atom) and the four lobes (ligands). The undistorted CoPc molecule appearance in STM images is an indication of low molecule-substrate hybridization. We addressed the CoPc electronic configuration

Figure 9: (a) Fe 2p XAS and (b) Co 2p XAS (b) spectra of CoPc 0.5 Å on Fe-O-Cu. Both spectra are measured at $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $T = 80$ K.

adsorbed on Fe-O-Cu surface by measuring Co $L_{2,3}$ XAS spectrum. Figure 9 (b) reports the Co L_3 XAS spectrum of well resolved substructure with features at 772.5, 774.6 and 776 eV. A reduction of the peak at low photon energy, usually attributed to Co $3d_z$ state, indicates a partial occupation of Co 3d state. The Co XAS line shape is consistent with a low moleculesubstrate hybridization. We found that the 1D CoPc arrangement on iron nanowire preserves almost unaltered the Co(Pc) electronic configuration of the free molecule. A partial unoccupied Co $3d_z$ state indicates a non-zero Co magnetic moment and a possible

magnetic coupling between iron nanostructure and Co(Pc)molecule. Similar results in terms of molecular appearance in STM images and the partial occupation of Co $3d_z$ orbital has been observed also on metal Au(778) vicinal surface,²⁰ but not on ferromagnetic nanostructures in our knowledge. Fe 0.3 ML on oxidized Cu(332) is expected to be ferromagnetically coupled at lower temperature. Iron nanowires on oxidized Cu(n,n,n-1) surfaces are therefore suitable templates for growing CoPc nanostructures.

Conclusions

CoPc molecules arrange in a 2D array when in contact with iron surfaces of crystalline ultrathin films, with the molecular plane parallel to the surface. The CoPc order is however lost as soon as the overlayer grows on top of interface, e.g. already at CoPC(1.5 ML). The molecule-ferromagnetic substrate interface interaction manifests as: (i) the broadening of Co(Pc) unoccupied molecular states independent of iron arrangement (pseudomorph-fcc or bcc); (ii) the broadening of N unoccupied molecular states dependent on the iron structure; (iii) the presence of molecular states in the proximity of E_F that participate in determining the electronic properties of the interface; (iv) Co(Pc) magnetic moment aligns accordingly to the magnetization of the underlying film. Interestingly, the strength of magnetic dichroism on Co atoms are the same for the 5ML Fe and 20ML Fe-thick, despite the large difference of net magnetization between the supporting films. This points to a direct one to one Co coupling with substrate Fe atoms, imposing different coordination to N molecular sites accordingly with the iron surface atomic structure. CoPc adsorbs selectively on iron wires grown on copper-oxide facets of Cu(332) forming therefore 1D chains. The weak perturbation of the CoPc electronic configuration upon adsorption and the ferromagnetic coupling to the contact substrate (surface, nanowire) opens interesting scenarios to be explored the magnetic properties of metallorganic hybrid interfaces.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the NFFA-Trieste international project of MIUR (Italy) and PRIN 2008 525SC7 contracts.

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